

SHORT NOTES

A New Thiazole Compound

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Following previous work on thiazole compounds^{1,2}, a new preparation containing two thiazole nuclei with two naphthalene nuclei has been achieved.

On condensing 2 moles of β -bromoacetylnaphthalene (I) with 1 mole of rubenic acid (II), 4,4'-(di- β -naphthyl)-2,2'-dithiazolyl (III) was smoothly obtained. It was formed in nice pale yellow flakes, easily soluble in sulphuric acid (conc.) developing a blood-red coloration.

Dithiazolyls generally show intense fluorescence and are halochromic; but this new compound does not show any fluorescence, neither in daylight nor in UV light.

The formation of this new preparation follows the equation:

1. Karrer *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 624.
2. Karrer and Forster, *ibid.*, 1945, 28, 315.
3. Karrer and Shukri, *ibid.*, 1945, 28, 820.
4. Karrer and Graf, *ibid.*, 1945, 28, 824.
5. Karrer and Forster, *ibid.*, 1947, 30, 1160.
6. Erlennmeyer *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, 35, 187.

Procedure.—In a 200 ml r.b. flask β -bromoacetylnaphthalene⁷ (m. p. ^{4°}) (5g, 2*M*) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (60 ml) with slight heating. A solution of ~~oxalic acid~~ ^{oxalic acid} (1.2g., 1*M*) in the same solvent (40 ml) was prepared and this solution was added to the first solution in the flask. The mixture was heated under reflux on a water bath for 5 hours and filtered in a Buchner funnel. Ten minutes after the beginning of heating, the condensation product started separating. The precipitate was washed first with cold ethanol followed by ether and left to dry. The mother liquor was evaporated to a small volume when some more of the compound was obtained. The raw material produced light grey flakes with metallic glaze, melting at 277°. The compound was crystallized from pyridine (80 ml), washed with absolute ethanol and ether, and left to dry.

Pure 4,4'-(di- β -naphthyl)-2,2'-dithiazolyl forms pale yellow glazing flakes, m.p. 278-79° (yield 3.6 g., 8.6%).

The product is soluble in H₂SO₄ (conc.) and hot pyridine, difficultly soluble in ethanol, ether, ethyl acetate but insoluble in benzene and water. [Found (dried in vacuum at 100° for 2 hours): C, 74.30; H, 4.10; N, 7.01. Calc. C, 74.28; H, 3.83; N, 6.66%].

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